

COMPLEX AND LATIN TERMS FOR WOMEN'S CLOTHES

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Compound words are words made up of two or more simple words. It is very difficult to define complex textile terms for women's clothing in English, because many terms are borrowed from other languages and it is difficult to understand the structure of the term. For example, the term *hourpelande* is derived from the French language, so it takes a lot of effort to determine its structure. But there are also terms whose structure is not difficult to determine. For example, *Bel-palto* is a vest (from the words *waist* and *coat*); *waist belt* - *waist belt*; *big coat* - *coat* (from the words *big* and *coat*); *undershirt* - *undershirt*; *baby stuart car* - a large wide-brimmed hat decorated with feathers and flowers; *gibsongirl* - a straw hat with a low crown and a narrow or raised brim; *robinhoodhat* - a cone-shaped hat decorated with long bird feathers; *pullover* - sweater (from the words *to pull* and *over*).

In the Tajik language, the model of complex structural terms is the most developed, and it is easier to determine the structure of complex terms, since the largest number of terms is original. For example: *sarandoz* - a tulle blanket for the bride's head (from the words *sar* and *andoz*); *poihoma* - prosperous (from the words *song* and *goma*); *chashmband* - a hair net that a woman should put on her face under a *burqa* (from the words *chashm* and *band*); *ezorband* - braid for tying flowerbeds; *dastrumol* - scarf (from the words *ber* and *römol*); *tustuppi* - a doppi with a flat square top (from the words *tus* and *tuppi*); *peshonaband* - gold-plated headband (from the words *peshona* and *tasma*); *sarostin* - sleeve cuffs decorated with a cross stitch (from the words *sar* and *austin*); *sargirak* - a light flowing robe-

shaped women's headdress with a tunic-like cut. Derived terms are the direct components of complex word forms, which are morphological formants - prefixes and suffixes. Let's see how the affixes denoting women's clothing work in textile terms.

In English, there are derivational terms formed using the suffix -ic. An example of such a word-formation in English is cambric, a very fine linen used for making shirts and dresses, forming the diminutive form of the word - ic .

In the Tajik language, diminutive suffixes are also used to form textile terms for women's clothing. Such suffixes are -ak and -cha. For example, a vest or a shirt is a sleeveless vest that is long up to the middle of the thigh; rumcha - a robe made of local silk of the kanausa type; short - vest; durracha - a small scarf; munisak - a turban hanging on the waist and folded on the side; gelak - a traditional tunic-shaped opening robe; Teapot - bib made of white cotton; Lachak is a headdress of old women.

From the examples given in the compared languages, it can be easily determined that the use of diminutive suffixes in Tajik is more derivative than in English. Ingliz tilidagi soʻz yasalishining affiks usuliga yana bir misol – chemisette soʻzidir. Bu soʻz frantsuzcha -ette qoʻshimchasi yordamida tuzilgan boʻlib, soʻzning ayollik kichraytiruvchi shaklini hosil qiladi. Masalan, jaket - koʻylagi; kasket - kasket.

In the Tajik language, a derivative word for women's clothing can be formed with the suffix -y, for example, lozimi - pants; Sozani is handmade silk fabric, etc.

Based on the examples of names formed with the help of affixes, we can conclude that the additional method of forming the names of women's clothing in the compared languages is not productive.

The structural analysis of terms in the dictionary of women's clothing showed that the system of word formation in the compared languages is a unique feature. For example, phrases are more effective as a way of forming words in English than

in Tajik. For example, blue jeans, chanel suit, top, morning dress, denim jacket, trench coat, stretch skinny pants, wool jacket with side zipper, etc., affixation and conjunction are most effective in Tajik language.

It is worth noting that the structural analysis of clothing vocabulary terms in comparable languages can also be carried out using the partial structure of complex terms. Based on this structure, the following models can be distinguished: Horse - horse. In Tajik, this model includes terms such as poyoma (from the nouns poy and joma), daströmöl (from the nouns datus and rumol), sarostin (from the nouns sar and ostin), bugoma (from the nouns bug and joma). , and others. In English, the model noun is a noun. refers to the terms gilet (from the nouns waist and coat) and rain (from the nouns rain and coat); A noun is a verb. This model is typical of the Tajik language. For example, sarandoz (from the verb sar and andoz), chashmband (from the verb chashm and toda), peshonaband (from the noun peshona and the verb toda), etc. In English, there is no defined term for such a model. Adjective is a noun. The conditions of this type of model are mainly related to the English language.

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